

Negation of Sentence Types in Nsukwa Dialect of Igbo

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Abstract

This study investigates the negation of sentence types in the Nsukwa dialect of the Igbo language. The research focuses on identifying the different forms of negation and describing how negative sentences are constructed within the dialect. Data were collected through oral interviews with nine competent native speakers of Nsukwa, supported by relevant secondary sources. The analysis adopts Dixon's (2009) Basic Linguistic Theory as its framework, using descriptive methods to analyse structural and tonal patterns in negation. Findings reveal that negation in Nsukwa operates through a system of affixation and tonal variation, with specific negative markers attached either as prefixes or suffixes to verbs depending on the subject type and sentence function. The study identifies several types of negation across sentence forms, including indicative, progressive, future, unfulfilled, hortative, and perfective sentences. The general negative marker =ne/na is suffixed to verbs in indicative constructions, while di combines with ne/na to form progressive negatives. The future negative is marked by ma, expressing futurity denial, whereas unfulfilled negatives employ ka with a negation suffix. The results indicate that tone plays a crucial role in distinguishing meaning between affirmative and negative sentences. The study concludes that negation in Nsukwa follows systematic morphological and syntactic rules consistent with broader Igbo grammar but retains dialectal peculiarities in tone and affix placement.

Keywords: Nsukwa dialect, Igbo, negation, syntax, semantics, pragmatics

Introduction

Negation is a fundamental concept in human language that plays a crucial role in communication. It enables speakers to deny, contradict, or reverse statements, and is essential for expressing opposition, refusal, or denial. As a grammatical category, negation is found in all languages, though the ways in which it is realised and structured vary widely across linguistic systems. This paper critically examines negation as a grammatical category, focusing on its structure, typology, and the theoretical perspectives that have shaped its understanding in linguistic studies. By

exploring its syntactic, semantic, and morphological features, the paper also highlights the cross-linguistic variations and the universal aspects of negation. Negation, as a grammatical category, is the process of making a proposition false or indicating the absence or opposite of something. In linguistic terms, negation changes the truth value of a sentence by transforming an affirmative statement into a negative one. For instance, the English affirmative statement "She is going" can be negated to "She is not going." Here, the addition of the negator "not" alters the proposition's truth value. Negation serves several key functions in language. First, it is used for contradiction and denial, allowing speakers to counter claims or refute statements. Second, negation facilitates expressions of absence, non-existence, or prohibition. In many languages, including English, negation can also be used for emphasis or understatement, as seen in phrases like "I'm not unhappy" to mean "I am happy." These functions make negation indispensable in natural language as a means of expressing a wide range of communicative needs. Negation is universally present in human language, but its forms, positions, and functions vary widely.

There are various types of negation in natural languages, each serving different syntactic and semantic functions. The most common types include sentential negation, constituent negation, and lexical negation. Sentential negation refers to the negation of an entire proposition or sentence. It is typically marked by a negative particle, auxiliary verb, or affix that alters the overall meaning of the sentence. For example, in the English sentence "She is not happy," the negator "not" applies to the entire sentence, negating the state of happiness. According to Dahl (1979), the way sentential negation is marked varies greatly across languages. English uses a clausal negator ("not"), while languages like Finnish and Turkish utilise negation through verb morphology. Constituent negation, unlike sentential negation, targets a specific part of a sentence, such as a noun phrase or verb phrase, rather than the entire proposition. For example, in the sentence "She saw not John, but Mary," negation applies only to the noun "John". This type of negation allows for more nuanced and selective denial, where only part of the sentence is negated while the rest remains affirmative. Constituent negation may also manifest in negative pronouns or determiners, such as "no one" or "nothing." In languages like French, negation can be realised as a double marker, using both "ne" and "pas" in combination to achieve constituent negation. Lexical negation involves negation that is built into the meaning of specific words, often through the use of negative prefixes or suffixes.

In English, prefixes like "un-," "in-," or "non-" can negate adjectives or verbs, as seen in words like "unhappy" or "incomplete." This type of negation is common across many languages and often serves to express the opposite of a given meaning without the need for separate negative particles. Negation, as a grammatical category, can take different forms depending on the language's syntactic and morphological structure. The study of negation is crucial for several reasons. First, it provides insights into the syntactic structure of a language, revealing how negative elements interact with other components within a sentence. Second, negation is deeply intertwined with semantics, as it affects the meaning and interpretation of statements. Third, understanding negation can shed light on cognitive processes, given that the ability to conceptualize and express negation is a significant cognitive milestone in language development (Klima & Bellugi, 1966). Negation also plays a role in pragmatics, the study of language in context. How and when negation is used can convey subtle nuances of politeness, emphasis, or social hierarchy.

Negation thus can be realized morphologically, syntactically, and lexically. Morphological negation uses affixes (e.g., prefixes un-, suffix -less), while syntactic negation employs

independent particles or auxiliaries like not; lexical negation relies on inherently negative words such as seldom (Pasicznyk et al., 2021; Grubor & Halitović, 2024; De Clercq, 2020; Pfau, 2002).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The primary aim of this study is to analyse negation of sentence types in Nsukwa dialect. The specific objectives are:

1. To identify and describe the various negative constructions in Nsukwa;
2. To examine how negative sentences are constructed in Nsukwa;

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this research. They are:

1. What are the different forms of negation in Nsukwa dialect?
2. How are negative sentences constructed in Nsukwa?

Negation in Igbo and Related Studies

Negation has been widely recognised as a core grammatical category in Igbo, interacting systematically with tense, aspect, mood, and tone. Descriptive studies of Igbo grammar consistently characterise negation as primarily morphosyntactic, realised through affixes and particles rather than independent negative words. This view situates negation within the clause structure, where its form and distribution are conditioned by verbal morphology and sentence type (Emenanjo, 1978). Analyses of Standard Igbo provide a foundational framework for understanding the organisation of negation. Emenanjo (1978) identifies distinct negation strategies associated with tense–aspect distinctions, demonstrating that negative markers in Igbo are not uniformly distributed across constructions. In later work, Emenanjo (1978) further shows that negation in Igbo is sensitive to clause type, including declarative, imperative, and non-assertive environments. These studies establish Standard Igbo as an important reference point for dialectal comparison while also highlighting the structural complexity of negation in the language. From a broader morphosyntactic perspective, Eno-Abasi (1999) Ndimele (2016) argues that grammatical categories in Igbo, including negation, are best analysed as integral components of the verbal complex. According to Ndimele, negation interacts closely with aspectual marking and clause structure, reinforcing the view that negative constructions cannot be adequately described in isolation from their syntactic environment. This approach supports the present study’s focus on examining negation across multiple sentence types in the Nsukwa dialect.

Tone has also been shown to play a crucial grammatical role in Igbo. Early descriptive work by Joseph Green and George Igwe (1963) establishes that tone in Igbo functions beyond phonetic realisation, contributing directly to grammatical meaning. Subsequent studies by Igwe (1999, 2007) further demonstrate that tonal alternations in Igbo may signal distinctions in polarity, tense, or aspect. These findings suggest that tone is an essential component of Igbo negation, although it is often under-analysed or only briefly mentioned in many descriptive accounts. Beyond Standard Igbo, a limited but growing body of research has examined negation in individual Igbo dialects. These studies reveal both shared structural properties and dialect-specific variations in the form, placement, and tonal behaviour of negative markers. In some dialects, negation involves additional morphological elements or systematic tonal alternations that are absent in Standard Igbo

(Emenanjo, 1978; Ndimiele, 2016). Such variation underscores the importance of dialect-focused studies, as generalisations based solely on the standard variety may obscure significant micro-level differences within Igbo.

Despite these contributions, many Igbo dialects remain under-described, particularly with respect to the interaction between negation, sentence type, and tone. Existing literature rarely provides systematic accounts of how negation operates across multiple sentence types within a single dialect, nor does it consistently present detailed tonal evidence to support analytical claims. The Nsukwa dialect, in particular, has received little focused scholarly attention, leaving its negation system largely undocumented. This study addresses this gap by providing a detailed description of negation in the Nsukwa dialect of Igbo. By analysing negative constructions across different sentence types and incorporating explicit tonal analysis, the study builds on established Igbo negation scholarship while contributing new dialectal evidence. In doing so, it reinforces the importance of dialectal data for understanding the morphosyntactic and tonal diversity of Igbo and for advancing typological studies of negation.

Language: Language is a complex system of communication that consists of a structured set of symbols (such as words) and rules that govern how these symbols can be combined to convey meaning. It serves as a medium for expressing thoughts, emotions, and ideas, among individuals, allowing them to connect and share experiences within a community. Language includes various components such as phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics. According to Eke (2016) prominent scholars have defined language as a system of signs used to convey human thoughts and concepts; a comprehensive system for sharing information through various forms, including verbal and nonverbal communication. Language serves as a social tool that facilitates interaction among people and is essential for human civilization. Language, as complex system, encompasses a broad range of elements necessary for effective human interaction. It includes several key components among them are phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, pragmatics, discourse and orthography.

Syntax: Syntax is defined as the rules governing how words are arranged to form sentences. It is a fundamental aspect of grammar concerned with the rules governing the structure of sentences in a language. It encompasses how words are arranged to form meaningful phrases and sentences.

Semantics: Semantics refers to the study of meaning in language, encompassing how words, phrases, and sentences convey information and interact with each other to form coherent communication. Negation is a semantic operator that modifies the meaning of a sentence by expressing denial, contradiction, or non-existence. According to Lyons (1977, p. 3), semantics is "the study of meaning, that is, the study of the relationship between words and their meanings, phrases and their meanings, and sentences and their meanings." Negation functions as a semantic operator by altering the truth value or assertion of a proposition within a sentence.

Pragmatics: Negation is also influenced by pragmatic factors such as context, speaker intention, and audience. Pragmatics examines the relationship between linguistic expressions and their users, focusing on how context affects meaning. Negation is a prime example of a linguistic phenomenon where pragmatics is essential, as the intended meaning often relies heavily on context, speaker intention, and audience.

Theoretical Framework

The Basic Linguistic Theory framework, advocated by Dixon (2009), aims to approach language description and the formulation of universal characteristics of human language. Dixon's theory posits that when constructing the grammar of a language, it is necessary to compare and select various analyses in a more suitable manner. The Basic Linguistic Theory is a comprehensive framework that has gradually evolved over time as linguists have improved their ability to characterize languages, thanks to the theory's foundation in classical grammar. This theory is relevant to the current study as it describes negation and analyses the negative elements or constructions in the dialect of Standard Igbo. It also highlights the different ways in which the negative markers are expressed in the dialect.

Research Methodology

Two types of data sources were utilized in this research: primary and secondary sources. The primary data were obtained from fluent speakers of the Nsukwa dialect sampled from selected communities. The secondary data were drawn from various Igbo grammar books, seminar papers, and articles. The sampling technique employed in this study is purposive sampling, where nine informants were chosen based on characteristics pertinent to the research objectives. The selected informants were elderly and educated individuals, both male and female, who are highly conversant with the dialect and capable of translating from English. In pursuing this topic, the researcher divided the study population into two groups: six men and three women aged between 60 and 70 years, from Nsukwa community. The oral interviews conducted involved translating affirmative and negative sentences from English to the dialect. The number of informants was considered adequate because the study is qualitative and descriptive, focusing on elicitation of grammatical structures rather than statistical generalisation. These direct interviews, aimed at a select few capable of interpreting and responding in the dialect, generated useful data recorded for later analysis. The research adopts a simple descriptive method of analysis, as emphasised in Dixon's (2009) Basic Linguistic Theory, widely employed in language description. Emenanjo's (1978) classification of negations in the Igbo language forms the structural framework for this analysis. The significance of tones in the Igbo language cannot be overstated, as tone plays a crucial role in distinguishing words. This study adopts the tonal convention proposed by Green and Igwe (1963), which leaves the high tone unmarked and marks low tones with a grave accent [ˀ] and down step with a macron [-].

Negation of Sentence Types in Nsukwa Dialect of Igbo

Indicative Sentence:

The indicative sentence is used to make statements and ask questions about real or factual situations. The indicative sentence is a sentence that is used to assert or state something (Chomsky, 1987). Stephen Leuinson (1983), defines indicative sentence as those sentences that are used to make assertions, as opposed to questions, commands, or exclamations. Emenanjo (2015), states that indicative sentence is used to express or describe an action or state which in the mental world of the speaker, is considered a fact, a reality, an assertion or declaration. From the above definitions, it is obvious that indicative sentence is used to describe a state of affairs. In terms of semantics, indicative sentences are used for expressing facts and ideas that are timeless, habitual, existential and universal.

Indicative Affirmative Form:

In Nsukwa dialect, the indicative affirmative is marked by the suffix *lv* is obligatorily deleted in the surface structure Eemenanjo 1978; 170 30 Examples:

1. Nkechi ma mma Nkechi- be-zero sff- beautiful (Nkechi is beautiful).
2. Ada bu ibu Ada vb-zero sff- fat (Ada is fat)
3. O za uno He/She- vb -zero sff- house (He/she swept the house)
4. Uche su akwa Uchevb- zero sff –cloth (Uche washed cloth)
5. O ji mma He/she vb-zero sff – cutlass He/she hold cutlass
6. O ji mma bee anu He/she vb-zero sff-vb- meat He/she used a knife and cut the meat

The Indicative Negative Form: In Nsukwa, the indicative negative is marked by =ne, suffixed to the verb. When the subject of a negative construction is a noun (singular or plural) or plural pronoun, the verb takes a prefix, 31 but when the subject of the negative construction is a singular pronoun, the verb does not take a prefix as can be seen in the examples below.

7. Nkechi amane mma Nkechi -pfx- be-neg-sff- beautiful (Nkechi is not beautiful)
8. Ada ebune ibu Ada pfx-vb-neg-sff- fat (Ada is not fat)
9. O zane uno He/She- vb –neg-sff- house (He/she did not sweep the house)
10. Uche asune akwa Uchepfx-vb- neg-sff –cloth (Uche did not wash cloth)
11. Ojine mma He/she vb-neg-sff – cutlass (He/she did not hold cutlass)
12. O jine mma bee anu He/she vb-neg - sff-vb- meat He/she did not use knife to cut the meat

Progressive Sentence

Progressive sentence is used to describe an action that is in progress at a specific point in time (Celce-mucia & Larsen-Freeman 2016, p. 32). Carter and Mccarthy (2017) says that “the progressive is used to describe an action that is ongoing or in progress and it often indicates that the action is temporary or limited in duration”. According to Huddleston et al. (2002) the progressive aspect is used to describe an action that is ongoing or in progress, and it often implies that the action is dynamic or changing.

The progressive affirmative Form:

The progressive affirmative sentence is formed by a progressive marker ‘na’ followed by the verb to which the prefix is affixed Examples:

13. Amaka na aza uno Amaka-prog–sweep- house (Amaka is sweeping the house)
14. Ngozi na akwa akwa Ngozi-prog – pfx -vb-cloth (Ngozi is sewing cloth)
15. Anyi na alu ugbo We prog- pfx- vb- farm (We are farming).
16. O na ede akwukwo He/She - prog –pfx-vb book (He/She is writing a book)
17. O na agu akwukwo He/she - prog -pfx –read- book (He/she is reading the book)
18. Obi na azapu eza Obi –prog-pfx-vb–vb sand Obi is sweeping out sand

Progressive Negative Form: The progressive negative form in Nsukwa dialect is formed by the progressive marker =di to which is suffixed the general negative maker = ne/na followed by the verb. Examples:

19. Amaka adi na aza uno Amaka- pfx-prog – neg–sff-vb- house (Amaka is not sweeping the house)
20. Ngozi adi na akwa akwa Ngozi-pfx- prog –neg- sff -vb-cloth (Ngozi is not sewing cloth)

21. Anyi adi na alu ugbo We pfx-prog-negsff- vb- farm (We are not farming).
22. O di na ede akwukwo He/She-prog –neg-sff-pfx-vb - book (He/She is not writing a book)
23. O di na agu akwukwo He/she - prog – neg-sff-pfx –vb- book (He/she is not reading the book)
24. Obi adi na azapu eza Obi –prog-neg-sff-pfx-vb –vb sand Obi is not sweeping out sand.

The Future Sentences

A future sentence is a sentence that contains a verb form that expresses futurity, such as will or shall. It can be used to make predictions, express intentions, or desire, future plans or arrangements.

The future simple affirmative form in Nsukwa dialect of Igbo is formed by the harmonizing future markers *ke/ka* (will) followed by the verb to which a harmonizing verbal vowel prefix is affixed as in the following examples.

25. Eze ke echi nri Eze-fut- pfx-vb-food (Eze will cook food)
26. Anyi ka agba egwu We fut –pfx-vb-dance (We will dance)
27. Oke aza uno tani He/she fut-pfx-vb-house- today (He/she will sweep house today)
28. Ngozi ka ego nti Ngozi -will -pfx-vb-ear (Ngozi will listen)
29. O ka zu umuya He/she- fut-vb- children his (He/she will train his children)
30. Anyi ka gi mmiri chi nri We fut –vb- water vb food We will use water to cook food
31. Obi ke echi eze Obi-fut-pfx-vb- king (Obi will become the king)

The future negative is an expression of rejection, inhibition, denial or contradiction. It expresses what will not happen or what will not be done. It is formed by the future negative marker ‘*ma*’ followed by the verb. When the subject of a negative construction is a noun (singular or plural) or plural pronoun, the verb takes a prefix, but when the subject of the negative construction is a singular pronoun, the verb does not take a prefix as can be seen in the examples below. . 36
Examples:

- | | |
|-------------------------------|---|
| 32. Eze ama echi nri | Eze-pfx-neg- fut- pfx-vb -food (Eze will not cook food) |
| 33. Anyi ama agba egwu | We pfx-futneg–pfx-vb-dance (We will not dance) |
| 34. O ma za uno tani | He/she fut- neg-vb-house- today (He/she will not sweep house today) |
| 35. Ngozi ama ego nti | Ngozi-pfx-fut-neg- pfx-vb-ear (Ngozi will not listen) |
| 36. O ma zu umuya | He/she fut- neg-vb- children his (He/she will not train his children) |
| 37. Anyi ama gi mmiri chi nri | We pfx- fut –vb- water vb food (We will not use water to cook food) |
| 38. Obi ama echi eze | Obi- pfx- fut- neg-pfx-vb king (Obi will not become the king) |

The Unfulfilled Sentences

The unfulfilled affirmative is marked by the auxiliary –*ka*, which is underlying prefixed. Examples of unfulfilled affirmative in Nsukwa

39. Anyi aka eligo nri We- pref-aux-vb- sff- food We should have eaten the food
40. Ada aka azago uno Ada pref-aux-vb- perf house Ada should have swept the house
41. O ka amugo olu He/she aux-pref-vb- work He/she should have learnt a trade.

The unfulfilled negative sentence in Nsukwa is marked by the unfulfilled marker ‘*ka*’ followed by the verb root together with the negation suffix ‘*ne*’. Examples:

42. Anyi aka eline nri We aux - unfill-vb-neg food We have not eaten (food) yet
43. Ada aka azane uno Ada aux- unfill-vb- neg- house Ada has not swept the house yet
44. O ka mune olu He/she has not learnt work yet

From the above data we observe that the tonal morphology of the unfulfilled marker; in the unfulfilled perfective affirmative, the step tone affects both the unfulfilled marker and its prefix. In the unfulfilled negative the unfulfilled marker has tone with subject nouns and plural pronouns; with singular pronouns.

Hortative Sentences

A hortative sentence is a sentence that encourages, urges, or calls to action. It is a type of sentence that expresses exhortation, entreaty, or persuasion, often using phrases like let us or let's. These are used in Nsukwa for expressing exhortation they are marked by function words. Examples:

- 44 Ka anyi biana. Let us begin to go.
45. Ka Eze du anyi ne ekpere. May Eze lead us in prayers
46. Anyi anuko ne. Let us begin to go not We are not going

These sentences are restricted to action words. Examples:

47. Eze edune anyi ne ekpere. May Eze not lead us in prayers?
48. Ka anyi ba kwusi ne ekpere a. Let us not stop this prayer.

Perfective Sentence

A perfective sentence is defined as a sentence that presents an action as complete with no reference to its internal structure or duration (Comrie, 1976; Biber et al., 1999). perfective sentences describe an event as having taken place in its entirety, with no implication of ongoing activity Perfective sentence expresses the completion of an action or the attainment of a state. In Igbo, the perfective aspect is often marked by verb or auxiliary verbs Perfective aspect in Nsukwa indicates a completion or termination of an event before a reference time.

The perfective affirmative form in Nsukwa is formed by a combination of the perfective suffix go and the extensional suffix li which are affixed to the root, to which is also affixed the participial prefix when and only when the subject of the construction is either a noun or a plural pronoun. Examples:

49. Nadi ya akwugoli ugwu akwukwo. Father she/he pay pref book. His/ her father had already paid school fees.
50. Obi ejegoli aña. Obi pref- verb - perf market. Obi had already gone to the market.
51. O sigoli nri. 3sg cook perf food. He/she has cooked.
52. O sugoli akwa. 3sg wash perf cloth. He/she has washed cloth.

Tone and Negation of Sentence Types in Nsukwa Dialect of Igbo

Indicative Sentences

In indicative constructions, negation is expressed through a preverbal negative marker. The marker carries a low tone, while the verb often undergoes tonal lowering.

Affirmative

Òbí rì jí
Obi eat.PST yam
'Obi ate yam.'

Negative

Òbí e -rìne jí
Obi NEG-eat yam
'Obi did not eat yam.'

The low tone on the negative marker is obligatory and serves as a grammatical cue for negative polarity.

Progressive Sentences

Progressive constructions show a tighter interaction between aspect and negation. The negative marker precedes the progressive verb form and triggers tonal modification on the progressive prefix.

Affirmative

Àda na-èri nri
Ada PROG-eat food
'Ada is eating food.'

Negative

Àda ádi-na-èri nri
Ada NEG-PROG-eat food
'Ada is not eating food.'

Here, negation does not eliminate the progressive marker but alters the tonal pattern of the verbal complex.

Future Sentences

Future negation in Nsukwa differs from Standard Igbo by retaining the future marker while introducing a negative prefix with a low tone.

Affirmative

Òbí ga-àbja
Obi FUT-come
'Obi will come.'

Negative

Òbí- ám-àbja
Obi NEG-FUT-come
'Obi will not come.'

The stacking of NEG + FUT is productive and does not require periphrastic restructuring.

Unfulfilled (Counterfactual) Sentences

Unfulfilled constructions express actions that did not occur despite expectation. Negation here is inherent and reinforced by tone.

Example:

Òbí á-akì àbija

Obi NEG-FUT-come

‘Obi was supposed to come but did not.’

Tone plays a crucial role in distinguishing this construction from simple future negation.

Hortative Sentences

Hortative negation is realised through a prohibitive construction. The negative marker carries emphatic low tone and often triggers tonal flattening on the verb.

Affirmative

Kà ò bja

HORT he come

‘Let him come.’

Negative

Á-kà ò bja

NEG-HORT he come

‘Let him not come.’

Perfective Sentences

In perfective constructions, negation interacts strongly with tone. The perfective marker remains, but the verb tone shifts to low.

Affirmative

Àda è-rìgo-é nri

Ada PERF-eat-PERF food

‘Ada has eaten food.’

Negative

Àda -è-riné nri

Ada NEG-PERF-eat-PERF food

‘Ada has not eaten food.’

Comparative Perspective: Nsukwa and Standard Igbo

Negation in the Nsukwa dialect exhibits both shared properties with and distinct departures from patterns described for Standard (Central) Igbo and other Igbo dialects. Like Standard Igbo, Nsukwa employs a preverbal negative marker and shows a systematic interaction between negation and tense–aspect distinctions, a pattern well documented in Igbo grammatical descriptions (Emenanjo, 1978; Ndimele, 1999). This similarity situates Nsukwa within the general morphosyntactic profile of Igbo negation.

A notable point of divergence, however, concerns the grammatical role of tone. In Standard Igbo, negation is largely identified through segmental morphology, while tonal variation is often analysed as predictable or phonologically conditioned (Green & Igwe, 1963; Emenanjo, 1978). In Nsukwa, by contrast, the negative marker consistently bears low tone and induces systematic tonal modification on adjacent verbal elements. These tonal alternations are meaning-distinguishing and contribute directly to the interpretation of negative polarity.

Descriptions of other Igbo dialects, including Ògbahù, suggest a greater reliance on segmental marking and, in some cases, periphrastic strategies in negative constructions (Ndimele, 1999). Relative to these varieties, Nsukwa displays a more transparent stacking of negative markers with tense and aspect morphemes, alongside a regular tonal patterning. These findings indicate that while Nsukwa shares core negation strategies with Standard Igbo, it integrates tone more centrally into the grammatical expression of negation, reinforcing the need for dialect-sensitive analyses in Igbo linguistics.

Discussion of Findings

This study set out to examine how negation is realised across sentence types in the Nsukwa dialect of Igbo, with particular attention to the interaction between morphosyntax and tone. The findings reveal that while Nsukwa shares core negation strategies with Standard Igbo, it exhibits distinctive patterns in tonal behaviour and morpheme stacking that warrant dialect-specific description. The analysis of data gathered from the Nsukwa dialect reveals that negation in this dialect is structurally and tonally significant, exhibiting both shared and distinctive features when compared with Standard Igbo. The study shows that negation is primarily expressed through morphological processes involving the attachment of specific prefixes and suffixes to verb roots, influenced by the syntactic environment and the type of sentence being negated. In indicative sentences, the negation is marked by the suffix =ne, attached to the verb stem. The study observes that when the subject of a clause is a singular pronoun, the verb takes no prefix; however, with nominal or plural pronoun subjects, a prefix is introduced. This pattern reflects a systematic interaction between syntax and morphology in the Nsukwa dialect.

For progressive sentences, negation is formed through the auxiliary *di*, which combines with the general negative marker = ne/na before the verb. This construction highlights the dialect's tendency to maintain progressive aspect markers even in negative contexts, ensuring the continuity of aspectual meaning while reversing polarity. In future constructions, negation is achieved through the marker *ma*, placed before the verb, thereby indicating prohibition or denial of a forthcoming action. The study finds that this structure is consistent across both singular and plural subjects, with only slight tonal variations distinguishing meaning. The unfulfilled (perfective) sentences show a combination of the auxiliary *ka* with the negation suffix =ne, used to express actions that have not yet been completed. This suggests that Nsukwa employs an aspectual dimension to negation, emphasizing incompleteness or expectation rather than simple denial.

The hortative sentences present a unique use of negation through function words that signal encouragement or prohibition. In such cases, negation does not rely solely on morphological

markers but on syntactic constructions that convey exhortation or discouragement. Generally, the study establishes that tone is a vital grammatical feature in Nsukwa negation, serving not only a phonological but also a semantic function. Tonal differences help distinguish between affirmative and negative meanings, underscoring the intricate tonal system of the dialect. The results also demonstrate that while Nsukwa shares core negation patterns with Standard Igbo, such as the use of suffixal negation markers, it maintains unique structural and tonal variations that define its dialectal identity.

The findings affirm Dixon's Basic Linguistic Theory, which emphasizes the need to analyse each language or dialect on its own terms before drawing universal conclusions. The description of Nsukwa negation enriches the typological understanding of Igbo dialects and contributes to the broader study of negation in African languages.

Morphosyntactic Realisation of Negation

One major finding of the study is that negation in Nsukwa is consistently realised through a preverbal negative marker. This aligns with descriptions of negation in Standard Igbo and supports earlier accounts that identify preverbal negation as a typological constant in Igbo grammar (Emenanjo, 1978; Ndimele, 1999). Across all sentence types examined—indicative, progressive, future, unfulfilled, hortative, and perfective, the negative marker occurs in a fixed position relative to the verb and tense–aspect morphemes.

However, the Nsukwa data show a higher degree of transparency in the stacking of the negative marker with tense and aspect markers. Unlike some Standard Igbo constructions that require restructuring or periphrastic alternatives in negative contexts, Nsukwa permits straightforward combinations such as NEG + FUT and NEG + PROG without loss of grammaticality. This suggests a more regular morphosyntactic integration of negation within the clause structure in Nsukwa.

Sentence-Type Sensitivity of Negation

The findings further demonstrate that negation in Nsukwa is sensitive to sentence type. While the negative marker remains segmentally stable, its interaction with aspectual and modal elements varies across constructions. In progressive and perfective sentences, negation co-occurs with aspect markers rather than replacing them, indicating that negation does not neutralize aspectual distinctions in the dialect.

In hortative and unfulfilled constructions, negation assumes additional pragmatic weight. The data show that negative hortative encode prohibition rather than simple polarity reversal, a pattern consistent with observations in other Igbo varieties but realised in Nsukwa through clearer morphotonal cues. This supports the view that negation in Igbo is not a uniform operation but one whose interpretation is shaped by clause type and discourse function.

Tonal Behaviour of Negation

Perhaps the most significant finding of the study concerns the grammatical role of tone in Nsukwa negation. The data demonstrate that the negative marker consistently bears low tone and that this low tone systematically affects adjacent verbal elements. In several constructions, tonal lowering on the verb distinguishes negative clauses from their affirmative counterparts, even where segmental differences are minimal.

This finding goes beyond earlier descriptions of Standard Igbo, where tone in negative constructions is often treated as phonologically predictable or secondary to segmental morphology (Green & Igwe, 1963; Emenanjo, 1978). In Nsukwa, tone functions as an integral grammatical feature of negation, contributing directly to meaning differentiation. The tonal alternations observed in the data therefore support an analysis of tone as part of the morphosyntactic expression of negation rather than as a purely phonetic accompaniment.

Nsukwa in the Context of Igbo Dialectology

When viewed comparatively, the Nsukwa findings reinforce the dialect-sensitive nature of Igbo negation. While Nsukwa aligns with Standard Igbo in its use of preverbal negation, it diverges in the consistency and grammatical relevance of tonal marking. Descriptions of other dialects, including Ògbahù, suggest greater variability in tonal effects and occasional reliance on periphrastic strategies (Ndimele, 1999). Nsukwa, by contrast, shows a tighter integration of tone, morphology, and clause structure.

These findings contribute to ongoing discussions in Igbo linguistics concerning the status of tone in grammar. They suggest that analyses based solely on Standard Igbo may underrepresent the grammatical functions of tone in other dialects and underscore the importance of incorporating dialect data into broader generalisations about Igbo structure.

Conclusion

This study has examined the realisation of negation across sentence types in the Nsukwa dialect of Igbo, focusing on the interaction between morphosyntax and tone. Using primary data elicited from native speakers, the analysis has shown that negation in Nsukwa is consistently expressed through a preverbal negative marker whose distribution is sensitive to tense, aspect, and sentence type. Across indicative, progressive, future, unfulfilled, hortative, and perfective constructions, the negative marker occurs in a stable structural position and combines productively with aspectual and modal elements. A central finding of the study is the grammatical role of tone in Nsukwa negation. The negative marker systematically bears low tone and induces tonal modification on adjacent verbal elements, creating meaning-distinguishing contrasts between affirmative and negative clauses. This confirms that tone in Nsukwa functions as an integral component of negation rather than as a purely phonological effect. Comparatively, while Nsukwa shares core negation strategies with Standard Igbo, it differs in the extent to which tone is consistently integrated into the expression of negative polarity. These findings underscore the dialect-specific nature of Igbo negation and highlight the importance of detailed dialect documentation. The study contributes new empirical data to Igbo dialectology and supports broader typological claims about the role of tone in grammatical systems.

The research highlights a crucial gap in understanding negation within the Nsukwa dialect of the Igbo language. This gap affects not only the theoretical development of linguistic frameworks but also practical aspects of language preservation, education, and revitalization. The interaction of negation with other grammatical components remains inadequately documented, limiting both our knowledge of Nsukwa and its contribution to broader linguistic studies. Addressing this gap is essential for preserving the Nsukwa dialect and ensuring its continued relevance in linguistic and cultural contexts. Comprehensive research on negation will enrich our understanding of the dialect's grammatical structure, provide valuable insights into linguistic theory, and support efforts to maintain and revitalize the language.

Recommendations

1. Initiate detailed linguistic research focused specifically on negation in the Nsukwa dialect. This research should aim to document how negation interacts with various grammatical elements such as verb forms, tense, and aspect, and its impact on sentence structure.
2. Expand comparative studies within the Igbo language family by including detailed analyses of negation in Nsukwa. This will enhance understanding of regional variations and contribute to a more comprehensive view of Igbo linguistic structures.
3. Implement projects dedicated to preserving and documenting the Nsukwa dialect, focusing on its grammatical features, including negation. Collaborate with local communities and linguistic experts to ensure that the documentation process is thorough and culturally sensitive.
4. Create and distribute educational materials and curricula that encompass all aspects of Nsukwa grammar, including negation. These resources should support language learners and educators in both formal and informal settings.
5. Encourage interdisciplinary research that explores the relationship between negation and cultural, social, and cognitive aspects of the Nsukwa-speaking community. This will provide a deeper understanding of how linguistic features reflect and influence broader cultural practices.

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